

INTEGRATING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ECONOMIC KNOWLEDGE IN STUDENT TRAINING: PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. *This article delves into the pedagogical and psychological aspects of integrating digital technologies and economic knowledge into the professional training of students in economics programs. It emphasizes how tools such as programmed education, computers, the Internet, and mobile applications are pivotal in enhancing students' competencies and professional skills. By adopting these technologies, educators can create an interactive and personalized learning environment that not only supports knowledge acquisition but also fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The article also explores the psychological impact of digital tools on students, including both the positive effects on cognitive development and potential challenges, such as digital dependence and the need for digital hygiene. Furthermore, this study highlights the importance of aligning educational practices with the evolving demands of the digital economy, preparing students to effectively utilize digital tools in their future careers.*

Keywords: *programmed education, digital technologies, computer, Internet, mobile application, cognitive development, digital hygiene.*

Introduction: The concept of informatization in higher education is rooted in the need to create an electronic information-educational environment. This environment, based on digital technologies, merges both traditional and contemporary information technologies, aligning with the demands of modern education. This approach is comprehensive and multidimensional, focusing not only on the incorporation of technology but also on analyzing its effective use within the higher education framework.

In today's educational landscape, the integration of digital tools has become essential to enhance the learning experience. Digital technologies offer opportunities to innovate and personalize the learning process, making it more engaging and relevant. In this regard, informatization isn't limited to merely adding digital tools to existing educational models. It encompasses a shift towards a more connected, interactive, and flexible approach that supports student-centered learning.

One critical aspect of the teaching process is motivating students to engage in their assignments actively. This involves presenting tasks in a structured manner, from simple to complex, and providing the necessary guidance to help students navigate these tasks. By encouraging students to progressively tackle more challenging assignments, educators can foster resilience and adaptability, key skills that are indispensable in today's dynamic job market. Through this process, teachers also cultivate students' abilities to think critically, solve problems, and apply their knowledge effectively.

Moreover, the teacher's role extends beyond mere instruction; it includes understanding students' perspectives, building meaningful connections, and analyzing interpersonal relationships

within the classroom. By promoting collaborative work and encouraging students to complete assignments in pairs or groups, educators facilitate a learning environment where students learn from each other. This collaborative approach, based on the principle that "by teaching others, I learn more deeply", enables students to develop communication and teamwork skills essential for their professional and personal growth.

The educational process is inherently complex, requiring a systematic approach to ensure its effectiveness. By applying such an approach, educators can better understand and utilize information technologies to support students, particularly those in economics programs. For these students, comprehending the role of information technologies in their field is crucial. This understanding begins by structuring educational content into two primary activities: teaching—the educator's role—and learning—the student's role. These two activities are not isolated but rather interconnected, each complementing the other. Together, they create a holistic educational experience that promotes mutual growth and understanding between teachers and students, fostering an environment where learning is seen as a collaborative journey.

Main Part: In higher education, the role of professors in delivering courses like "Information and Communication Technologies and Systems in Economics" goes beyond mere content delivery. This process represents a multifaceted approach to education, involving complex interactions between the acquisition of subject-specific knowledge and its application in practical, professional contexts. As digital technologies increasingly permeate the field of economics, students must not only understand ICT concepts but also apply these tools to solve real-world economic problems. Thus, professional training in economics education encompasses two primary activities: first, the acquisition of theoretical knowledge in ICT as it relates to economics, and second, the practical application of this knowledge in real-life economic scenarios.

Modern education demands a shift from traditional didactic methods to approaches that promote independent problem-solving and critical thinking. Effective learning management now emphasizes fostering students' creative and autonomous capabilities, thus preparing them to tackle complex challenges independently. Beyond the passive reception of information, students are encouraged to engage actively in the learning process, developing skills that are integral to lifelong learning. Psychological elements such as perception, attention, memory, imagination, and logical reasoning are foundational to this process, allowing students to process, retain, and apply knowledge in innovative ways.

Scholars such as E. Goziyev have highlighted the profound impact that information has on human cognitive functions, while V. Karimova's research emphasizes the importance of information-psychological security. Karimova's work establishes a framework for understanding how individuals can protect themselves from information-related threats, such as communicative stress and information overload, which are increasingly relevant in our digitally connected world. Building on these ideas, researchers like S. Jalilova and N. Safayev have examined how information influences students' cognitive engagement and motivation in learning environments. Similarly, A. Ismanova and colleagues have developed pedagogical mechanisms for cultivating information consumption habits, which are essential for fostering critical thinking and media literacy among students.

Further research by I.V. Robert investigates the psychological and pedagogical dimensions of teaching ICT, emphasizing how digital tools can transform learning experiences. Robert notes that modern digital platforms enhance learning by supporting personalized and adaptive learning

experiences, where students can engage with content in ways that are tailored to their individual needs and learning styles. For instance, the integration of computer technologies into educational settings enables students to visualize complex economic concepts through simulations and interactive software, which deepens their understanding and facilitates higher-order thinking.

The pedagogical possibilities of computer technology have been notably discussed by A.P. Yershov, who argued that computers serve as an ideal tool for active learning. Computers not only facilitate student engagement but also support interactive learning methods, where students collaborate and learn from each other in real-time. Key advantages include:

Enhanced collaboration: Digital platforms encourage peer interaction, enabling students to work together on problem-solving tasks, which promotes teamwork and the exchange of ideas.

Individualized learning: Through adaptive learning systems, students can progress at their own pace, receiving customized feedback that caters to their specific learning needs.

Comprehensive assessment: Digital tools provide a means of tracking student progress and assessing their understanding across multiple stages of the learning process. By integrating these technologies, educators can monitor and support student development more effectively.

Development of digital literacy: As students work with advanced technologies, they gain proficiency in digital tools that are directly applicable to professional settings in economics and other fields.

Incorporating digital technologies into economics education provides students with access to resources that enhance their learning. For example, platforms that support distance learning expand access to quality education, regardless of geographical limitations. Digital technologies also enable students to interact with diverse information formats, including audio, visual, animation, and large datasets, which contribute to a richer, multi-modal learning experience. As students engage with these resources, they acquire skills that are critical for navigating the data-intensive economy.

Through our research, we have found that integrating digital technologies and economic knowledge into the curriculum not only enhances students' intellectual abilities but also shapes their psychological development. The use of computers and mobile applications in the learning process promotes skills in information retrieval, analysis, and synthesis, while also helping students cultivate habits of lifelong learning. These tools serve as both intermediaries and facilitators, bridging the gap between academic knowledge and real-world applications. Moreover, by providing students with opportunities to interact with digital technologies, we prepare them for the realities of a digital economy, where technological fluency is a fundamental requirement.

However, it is essential to acknowledge the potential psychological effects of prolonged exposure to computer technology. Some researchers have cautioned that excessive computer use can contribute to cognitive strain, anxiety, and dependency. For instance, A.V. Minakov has outlined several adverse effects associated with digital environments, such as information fatigue, social isolation, and diminished attention spans. These concerns highlight the need for educators to strike a balance, ensuring that digital tools are used in ways that support positive cognitive and psychological outcomes for students.

In conclusion, by carefully incorporating digital technologies into the curriculum, educators in higher education can support students in developing the competencies they need to succeed in a digital world. This approach requires a deep understanding of both the educational

and psychological impacts of technology, and a commitment to fostering environments where students can learn, collaborate, and grow.

The rapid evolution of informatization and the integration of digital technologies into virtually every aspect of human activity have brought new challenges and research opportunities. This widespread use of technology has introduced various psychological and behavioral issues, such as the excessive consumption of irrelevant information, over-reliance on social media, and the development of computer and internet addiction. These phenomena underscore the need to examine human-computer interactions from psychological and social perspectives and to explore effective strategies for utilizing information technologies productively.

In the realm of education, the application of digital technologies must be guided by a thoughtful consideration of psychological and pedagogical principles. To maximize the effectiveness of these tools, it is essential to align educational strategies with the psycho-physiological and psychological characteristics of students. This approach involves organizing learning experiences that cater to diverse cognitive and emotional needs, recommending the use of information technologies at each educational stage, and ensuring that these tools are employed under optimal conditions. When such factors are integrated into the design of digital learning environments, they can enhance learning outcomes and improve student engagement.

The dynamics of student-computer interaction require careful analysis, particularly regarding the psychological and social effects of prolonged technology use. This field of study has revealed both the benefits and drawbacks of technology on cognitive and emotional well-being. For instance, individuals who have long-term interactions with computers tend to exhibit certain psychological traits, such as resilience, goal-oriented behavior, and a preference for independent decision-making. These individuals often show a strong desire for autonomy and demonstrate creativity and productivity-focused mindsets. However, they may also face challenges in areas such as empathy, emotional regulation, and conflict resolution. Prolonged computer use has been associated with decreased emotional sensitivity, increased social isolation, and a tendency towards self-centeredness, which may impair social interactions and lead to difficulties in collaborative settings.

An additional concern is the impact of technology-related stress on students. Many students experience anxiety linked to their interactions with computers, often driven by fears of underperformance, receiving low grades, or failing to keep pace with peers. This anxiety can manifest as “computer stress,” characterized by symptoms such as insomnia, visual fatigue, headaches, chronic exhaustion, depressive moods, and communication difficulties. These symptoms highlight the need for a balanced approach to technology use in educational contexts, where students are encouraged to engage with digital tools in ways that support their cognitive and emotional health.

The psychological and social implications of extensive technology use are multifaceted. While technology offers unparalleled access to information and educational resources, it also poses risks that warrant attention. Research has shown that excessive exposure to digital environments can lead to issues like information overload, internet addiction, and a narrowing of interests. A.V. Minakov, for example, points out that the digital environment often brings about psychological challenges, such as digital fatigue and internet addiction, which may reduce the scope of intellectual development and impoverish social interactions. These factors call for a

comprehensive understanding of both the beneficial and adverse effects of technology use, emphasizing the importance of responsible digital habits.

The future of educational technology will require strategies that address these psychological dimensions, supporting students in building resilience against potential negative impacts. To this end, educational institutions can play a proactive role by promoting digital literacy and fostering a culture of balanced technology use. By creating structured and supportive digital environments, educators can help students develop a positive relationship with technology, one that enhances their intellectual growth while safeguarding their psychological well-being.

Kimberly Young defines "Internet addiction" as a broad term encompassing various problematic behaviors associated with a lack of control over one's desires and impulses. However, if educators emphasize the positive aspects of Internet technologies, they can shape students' understanding and teach them to use the Internet effectively within the learning process. The advantages of information technology in education include enabling students to independently search for information, access extensive informational resources, and engage actively with these materials. Through computer-based learning, students are immersed in different environments, fostering a creative approach to problem-solving. When students are assigned tasks that involve Internet use, they can develop diverse viewpoints and contribute to democratizing the learning experience by moving away from authoritarian instructional methods.

In the educational context, one of the key challenges of utilizing digital technology is identifying and nurturing talent, preparing gifted students, and creating personalized learning programs that can adapt to individual needs. Talent in specific fields of human activity, especially in logic and mathematical ability, is often underexplored. Studies by researchers such as Y.D. Babayeva and N.B. Berezanskaya indicate that the psychological impact of informatization can help reveal the multidimensional characteristics of students. These scholars note that using information technologies in education can foster creativity, enhance personal and communicative skills, and underscore the role of social factors in learning.

Moreover, as students increasingly rely on computers, attention must be paid to issues of personal hygiene and health. Excessive computer use can lead to physical problems, such as visual strain and nervous tension. As a result, integrating digital technologies into the educational process involves more than simply introducing new tools; it requires a comprehensive approach based on modern psychological and pedagogical theories. Educators must design and implement new instructional programs and lesson plans that address these considerations, ensuring that the informatization and computerization of the curriculum are conducted in ways that align with the psychological traits of both teachers and students.

The success of students in meeting educational objectives depends on their readiness and intellectual development, which are influenced by elements of creative problem-solving. By integrating digital technologies with economic knowledge in the curriculum, educators can enhance students' motivation, strengthen their understanding of academic subjects, and cultivate their ability to tackle creative tasks. Such an integrated approach not only improves students' grasp of complex topics but also prepares them for the evolving demands of a digital economy. This process also underscores the necessity of a thoughtful balance between digital engagement and the promotion of overall health, highlighting the role of educators in guiding students toward a balanced use of technology in both educational and personal contexts.

Researcher N.Y. Marchuk, in his article titled “Psychological and Pedagogical Aspects of Distance Learning,” explores the historical development of distance education, its advantages over traditional education, and various models of distance learning. Marchuk emphasizes that compared to younger students, older adults often demonstrate advanced psychological traits, such as cognitive maturity, emotional resilience, motivational clarity, and goal-setting abilities. Additionally, they tend to approach educational materials with a systematic method, progressing from simple to complex concepts. Furthermore, they integrate pedagogical technologies into the learning process, which enriches their understanding and application of subjects being studied.

Conclusion. Incorporating digital technologies and economic knowledge into the professional training of economics students in higher education requires careful attention to several pedagogical aspects:

Career-oriented content development: This involves creating and implementing practical, laboratory, and independent assignments that align with professional goals.

Integration of digital technologies and economic knowledge: Using digital tools in lessons enhances students' understanding of both ICT and economics, fostering skills that are relevant to their careers.

Development of digital and economic competencies: Cultivating essential digital literacy and economic skills equips students for the demands of their field.

Achievement of educational and developmental goals: Incorporating individualized approaches ensures that students' unique abilities and potential are considered within the learning environment.

Self-assessment and critical decision-making: Enabling students to critically evaluate available information, select what is most pertinent, and make informed decisions strengthens their analytical capabilities.

Additionally, attention must be given to the following psychological aspects:

Addressing Internet dependency: Educators should help students understand the risks of excessive Internet use, such as addiction or social withdrawal, and encourage healthier digital habits.

Enhancing memory for quick learning: Supporting students in developing strong memory skills can facilitate faster comprehension and retention of complex subjects.

Promoting motivation and capability development: By fostering intrinsic motivation, students are more likely to engage in sustained learning and personal growth.

Focusing on memory-related learning strategies: Encouraging persistence, goal setting, and a concentration on learning objectives can improve the ability to absorb and retain new knowledge.

Cultivating patience and curiosity: Encouraging students to approach new knowledge with patience and enthusiasm is vital for long-term educational success.

The integration of digital technologies into the educational process requires more than a simple addition of tools; it demands the creation and implementation of new programs and lesson plans rooted in modern psychological and pedagogical theories. The future of digital and computer-aided education relies on the intelligent restructuring of teaching processes that align with the psychological characteristics of both students and educators.

For students to successfully fulfill educational objectives, they need not only intellectual readiness but also elements of creative problem-solving and a commitment to continuous improvement. By incorporating digital technologies alongside economic knowledge, educators

can enhance students' motivation, deepen their understanding of academic subjects, and better prepare them for the challenges of a digital and economically interconnected world.

REFERENCES

1. Ғозиев Э. Умумий психология. Дарслик. –Т: 2002. 238-б.
2. Каримова В.М. Ижтимоий психология. Дарслик. Тошкент. 2012. -172 б.
3. Давлатов О.Ғ. Талабаларда ахборот хавфсизлигини таъминлаш компетентлигини тарихий-маданий мерос воситасида ривожлантириш. Педагогика фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси автореферати. –Тошкент, 2018. -57 б.
4. Балина Т.Н. Психолого-педагогические аспекты компьютерного обучения. Вестник Таганрогского института управления и экономике. №1/2009. Стр. 105-108.
5. Семенова З.В. Развитие углубленного обучения информатике в условиях модернизации школьного образования. Дисс. Докт. пед. наук. - Москва, 2004 – 406 с.
6. Скворцова Л. Психологические проблемы использования компьютерных технологий. 1 августа 2010 г.
7. Янг К. Интернет-зависимость вчера и сегодня: пер. с англ. / К. Янг // Интернет-зависимость: психологическая природа и динамика развития / Под ред. А.Е. Войскунского. – М.: Акрополь, 2009. – С. 251–252.
8. Бабаева Ю.Д., Березанская Н.Б., Васильев И.А. и др. Смысловая теория мышления // Вестник Московского университета. Сер. 14. Психология. 2008. № 2. С. 26-58.
9. Марчук Н.Ю. Психолого-педагогические особенности дистанционного обучения. Педагогическое образование в России. 2013. № 4. Стр. 78-85.
10. Kayumova N.A, Fayziyeva Sh.F. Computer Networks Use of Vlan (Virtual Local Area Network) Technology in Modelling and Grouping. Eurasian Research Bulletin www.geniusjournals.org Page | 156
11. Сурупов Б.М. Олий таълимда ахборот-таълим муҳитини яратиш ва ундан фойдаланишнинг имкониятлари. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/oliy-talimda-ahborot-talim-mu-itini-yaratish-va-undan-foydalanishning-imkoniyatlari>
12. Maydonovich S.B. (2020). Teaching students automation of financial reports of the company by using spreadsheet system in ms excel. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(1).
13. Сурупов Б.М. (2018). Информатика фанида стандарт функцияларни ўқитишнинг узлуксизлиги. // “Замонвай таълим” (“Современное образование”) илмий-амалий оммабоп журнали (Узбекистан), № 4, 62-67 б.
14. Сурупов Б.М. (2020). Дастурий маҳсулотлардан фойдаланиб инновацион фаолиятни тижоратлаштириш. Современное образование (Узбекистан), // “Замонвай таълим” (“Современное образование”) илмий-амалий оммабоп журнали (Узбекистан), № 2 (87), 3-8 б.
15. Сурупов Б.М. (2023). Мобиль иловалар асосида талабаларнинг замонавий билимларни ўзлаштириш механизмлари. // “Замонвай таълим” (“Современное образование”) илмий-амалий оммабоп журнали (Узбекистан), № 5 (126), 10-17 б.